

A hermeneutic review of how spatial weights are conceptualised in GIScience

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Abstract:

Spatial weights are often treated as technical tools in spatial analysis, yet the ideas and assumptions shaping them often go unquestioned. This research shares early results from a broader interpretive study exploring how the academic literature, particularly in human geography, frames and defines these weights. Drawing from a structured review of more than 16,000 articles indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, the study uses a filtering and clustering approach to identify a manageable group of 30 empirical studies for detailed analysis.

The selection process began with narrowing the dataset down to 638 abstracts. After that, a two-step screening was applied using set inclusion standards and agreement among the authors to settle on 30 studies that would undergo a qualitative reading. Our methodological innovation lies in combining structured corpus selection with hermeneutic inquiry, allowing for a deeper look into the ideas and assumptions that guide methodological decisions involving spatial weights.

At the centre of this research is one key question: What kinds of meaning do researchers attribute to “space” when they apply spatial weights? Since such meanings are usually implied rather than clearly stated, a hermeneutic approach is used since it enables researchers to interpret underlying positions. Early findings already show repeating patterns in how scholars frame the concept of space through their chosen methods.

This work opens up space for broader conversations about what spatial concepts actually mean in spatial analysis practice, encouraging a more thoughtful and reflective approach to spatial modelling. By uncovering and interpreting the assumptions embedded in methodological choices, we aim to promote more reflexive spatial modelling practices, not just technical precision. It contributes to growing efforts to include deeper interpretive practices within spatial analysis and foster researcher community self-awareness and critical engagement.

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